

Managing Organizational Competencies for Office Managers' Performance and Economic Recovery in Public Parastatals in Rivers State

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the managing organizational competencies for office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers state. The researcher developed three specific objectives and three research questions that guided the study. three null hypotheses were also tested at .05 alpha level of significance. The target population of this study comprised one hundred and twenty-two (122) office managers in public parastatals in Rivers State. Organizational Competencies of Office Managers and Employees' Performance in Public Parastatals Questionnaire" was developed and used for the study. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation. The research instrument was validated by three (3) experts from the faculty of Education in University of Port Harcourt. The experts were selected for the fact that they acquired the experts' knowledge and experience in text construction and have been using similar research instrument in eliciting information for the purpose of study. To establish the reliability of the instruments, test re-test method was employed by the researcher. The coefficient of the responses was computed using Pearson's' Product Moment Correlation Coefficient of data collected with the reliability score of 0.81, thus confirming that the instrument is reliable hence, measured what they purported to measure. The researcher employed the services of two (2) research assistants. The research assistants were used to administer the instrument to the respondents. The research assistants were briefed and trained on how to administer and retrieve the instrument for the study. Data collected was analyzed using item by item analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the responses of the three (3) research questions, while the three (3) hypotheses were tested using Pearsons' Product Moment Correlation at of 0.05 level of significance. Based on the results of the findings, the researcher recommends that: Organizational Competencies of Office Managers and Employees Performance in public parastatals Rivers State, as it will enhance their work performance. Office Managers in private & public parastatals should explore communication skills to enable effectively carryout their administrative duties, Office Managers should update their information communication and technology skills as it has the ability to enhance work performance and Office Managers should be given the opportunity be trained and retrain on other office managerial skills to enhance their performance.

Keywords: Managing, Organizational Competencies, Office Managers' Performance, Economic Recovery

INTRODUCTION

Office automation occasioned by technological innovations, has to a great extent changed the ways and means of carrying out functions in contemporary business organizations globally. This development has consequently compelled organizations (public and private) to adapt to these technological innovations in order to remain competitive and survive in the long-term turbulent business world (Ejekam, 2021). These technological changes have also tremendously altered the duties performed by office managers in modern offices as they are exposed to office technology and innovations, which require relevant organizational competencies in order to effectively perform their duties (Amaewhule & Wolugbom, 2021). Corroborating these views, Amadi, Ogwunte, Egbunefu and Aruchi (2019) observed that the evolution of modern office technology in business organizations coupled with new management techniques have completely changed old work habits and triggered off a new business orientation; thus, making moribund the old methods of office transactions. Today, there is hardly any modern business organization that operates without the use of one form of modern office technology or the other (Azih, 2022). Thus, the acquisition of relevant organizational competencies has become imperative for office managers to effectively perform their duties.

The International Atomic Energy Agency (2022) defined competency as a combination of skills, knowledge, attributes and behaviours that enables an individual to perform a task or an activity successfully within a given job. Competencies are observable behaviours that can be measured and evaluated, and thus are essential in terms of defining job requirements and recruiting, retaining and developing staff (International Atomic Energy Agency, 2022). Competencies enable the staff of an organization to have a clear understanding of the behaviours to be exhibited and the levels of performance expected in order to achieve organizational goals. They provide the individual with an indication of the behaviours and actions that will be valued, recognized and rewarded (International Atomic Energy Agency, 2022).

In their own view, Amadi, Ogwunte, Egbunefu and Aruchi (2019) described competency as the capabilities and abilities required for maximum performance of a task. Similarly, Dickson (2021) defined competency as an essential knowledge and skill obtainable in a profession and those which the professionals in the field must develop and possess in order to operate at optimal level of acquisition and functioning. It comprises of knowledge, skills, abilities, traits and behaviours acquired through education, training, experience, or natural abilities that allow an individual to perform a task within a specific function or job in an organization (Amaewhule & Wolugbom, 2021). It also denotes a blend of awareness, proficiency, approach, worth and individual attributes that allow the worker to behave professionally and fittingly in a situation, deploying them in a more articulate way (Amaewhule & Wolugbom, 2021).

Also in agreement with the above definitions, Ezenwafor and Okeke (2018) stated that competency in modern office requires a combination of skills, knowledge, practical behaviours and attributes that are directly related to successful performance on the job in an organization. Furthermore, Warier (2018) defined competency as “The knowledge, skills and attributes (KSA) that differentiates superior performers from others in every sphere of life”. The development of accurate and appropriate competencies results in enhanced organizational learning, performance management while maximizing the usage of the organizational intangible assets.

The importance of organizational competencies of office managers has increased overtime due to the strategic roles they play in contemporary work environment. It is a high critical factor to successful performance of the jobs of office managers (Amaewhule & Wolugbom, 2021). According to Amaewhule and Wolugbom (2021), these organizational competencies include: communication competencies, office management competencies, information technology competencies, human relations competencies, problem solving competencies, decision-making competencies, secretarial abilities, etc. To Egbunefu (2023), such competencies include but not limited to: teamwork competencies, communications competencies, human relations competencies, self-development competencies, among others.

On the other hand, employee performance refers to how well an employee performs at work and then afterwards measured against the generally accepted indicators of performance standards that are set by the organizations (Mandisahona, 2018). Employee performance is generally seen by scholars as the behavioural aspect that defines the way in which organizations, teams and individual employees get work done (Daddie, Nwiko, Iroanwusi & Ogbobula; 2018). Armstrong, (2020) described employee performance as the output record of a specific job function or activity at a given time. Similarly, Motowidlo and Kell (2019) describe it as the total expected value to the organization of the discrete behavioural episodes that an individual carries out over a standard period of time. It can also be viewed as how efficiently employees accomplish

their duties (Torlak & Kuzek, 201.9) and are usually measured through multi dimensions (Deslie, 2015; Pradhan & Jena, 2017, Arugu, 2020).

Employee performance is usually based on the employee's knowledge, skill, expertise and behaviour necessary to perform the job (Wen, Ho, Kelana, Othman & Syed, 2019). This implies that the realization of organizational objectives is tied to the ability of the employees to perform their assigned duty at the appropriate time. In line with this view, Arugu (2020) noted that it is then the major task of management of organizations to put in place measures and structures that promote greater achievements and high-performance levels for the employees and organization.

Therefore, the competency of an office manager is considered an important tool for improved employee performance outcome. In other words, the combination of skills, knowledge, attributes and behaviours of the office manager are vital in stimulating improved employee performance outcome (Obiekwe, 2018). This is because an organization is an entity which is made up of people working together to achieve organizational goals and objective and as such require competencies of the office manager to be realized (Udoh, 2020). Furthermore, Hakala (2018) pointed out that performance measurement is an on-going activity for all managers and their subordinates; and the measurement and indicators are: quantity, quality, timeliness, and cost-effectiveness.

Normally in Nigeria, ministries provide the relevant functions that are required to enable the government to function. Each ministry is headed by a permanent secretary who reports to a minister in the government cabinet. However, some government functions are provided by commissions or parastatals (government owned corporation) that may be independent or associated with a ministry (Uduh, 2020). According to Okoro (2020), parastatals are one of the main components of the public sector. They are one of the types of organization established under Acts of Parliament which makes them legal entities. These legal entities are required to discharge various obligations in the economic, social landscape and other sectors; hence playing a pivotal role in the nation's development. Parastatals are involved in various areas of activities comprising among others, industry, agriculture, commerce, tourism, health, transport, culture and education (Okoro, 2020).

The Act establishing a parastatal provides the legal framework and parameters within which it should operate. Parastatals have Board of Directors or Council in some instances which are mandated to set the policies and direction of the organization (Iwari, 2021). In most cases, a director general or general manager (that is chief executive officer) is appointed to implement the decisions of the Board or Council and to be responsible for the day-to-day management of the organization. Each parastatal is overseen by a ministry and a representative of the latter equally forms part of the Board or Council with a view to ensuring that government policies are effectively disseminated to the relevant bodies and subsequently the decisions and actions taken are according to these policies (Ngagi & Malel, 2021).

Sadly, the management of public parastatals generally in Nigeria and Rivers State in particular is a sad tale of failures and inability to accomplish the purposes they were created to achieve (Okeke, Onuorah, & Okonkwo, 2016, Esu, 2020). As earlier stated above, the public parastatals were established to act as the pivot to propel economic and social development in areas of need. However, most of them operate at high losses and on government subsidies and support to survive; thereby, constituting a financial burden to the government due they are not self-sustaining (Okeke, Onuorah, & Okonkwo, 2016, Esu, 2020, Agagu,

2021). This unacceptable development calls for the re-examination of the influence of the organizational competencies of office managers on employees' performance.

Statement of the Problem

In public parastatals in Rivers State, offices have been largely equipped with modern technological equipment and machines such as computers for their operations. However, despite these provisions, Amadi, Ogwunte, Egbunefu and Aruchi (2020) observed that many office managers find it difficult to manage these modern technological equipment and machines in their operations; hence some of the modern equipment and machines in most public parastatals in Rivers State lie idle without being put to functional optimal use and where it is being used, only typing of textual documents are done with it. Most times, their works are subcontracted to private organizations to perform. This exposes official documents to the public even before they are signed for implementation. These ineffective performances indicate that office managers in these public parastatals lack the relevant organizational competencies to successfully carry out their functions.

This apart, it has also been observed that managers in public parastatals in Rivers State tend to have lukewarm attitude towards performing their managerial functions or tasks and any other engagements involving them; resulting to: negative attitude to work; poor performance; low productivity; lack of interest in one's job; excessive absenteeism rate; excessive complaints; high rejects or low quality output; high incidence of accidents; and insubordination of employees (Anyadighibe, Nsobiari, Ezekiel & Eneh, 2022). Today, most of the public parastatals now run at high operating losses and depend on government subsidies and support to survive; thereby constituting a financial burden to government because they are not self-sustaining. For these problems to be solved there is need to ascertain the organizational competencies of office managers and employees' performance in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of this study was to determine the managing organizational competencies for office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State. Specifically, the study attempted to:

1. Determine the management of teamwork competencies for office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.
2. Determine the management of communication competencies for office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.
3. Determine the management of human relations competencies for office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide this study:

1. To what extent does management of teamwork competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does management of communication competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does management of human relations competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between management of teamwork competencies and office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between management of communication competencies and office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between management of human relations competencies and office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research design was selected for this study. The area of study was parastatals in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The population of this study comprised one hundred and twenty-two (122) office managers in public parastatals in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Due to the manageable size of the population of the study, the entire one hundred and twenty-two (122) were used for the study.

A structured 4 points scaled questionnaire titled "Organizational Competencies of Office Managers and Employees' Performance in Public Parastatals Questionnaire" was developed and used for the study. To ascertain the validity, the research instrument was given to two experts in Business Education and one measurement and evaluation expert; all in the Faculty of Education; to assess the relevance of each item in the research instrument; clarity of purpose and objectivity. The corrections made by the experts (validators) were effected in the final draft of the questionnaire. The scores were tested for reliability (consistency in measurement) using the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient. The entire alpha coefficients of the individual constructs were above the recommended cut-off (0.74), and therefore considered good. The researcher in conjunction with two research assistants administered copies of the research instrument (or questionnaire) to respondents. This measure ensured a high return of the completed questionnaires and correct filling. The researcher also ensured that the questionnaire that was administered were properly filled and collected after an interval of two weeks. The data collected were analyzed using tables, frequencies and mean to answer the research questions while Pearson's product moment correlation analysis was performed to test the null hypotheses in order to determine whether they will be accepted or rejected. A criterion (benchmark) mean of 2.50 and above was considered as the minimum for acceptance, while any item with a criterion mean below 2.50 was considered as rejection; given that

$$\frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.50.$$

RESULT

Research Question 1: To what extent does management of teamwork competencies influence office managers’ performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State?

Table 1 Mean and Standard Deviation on management of teamwork competencies influence office managers’ performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State (N = 122)

S/ N	Item Statements	Male 68			Female = 54		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remarks	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1.	In consultation with the supervisor, recognizes and seizes opportunities to create a collaborative team in support of achieving organizational objectives	2.96	0.89	ME	3.18	0.89	HE
2.	Ensures that his/her team complies with the applicable regulations, rules and policies of their organization.	2.82	0.91	ME	3.17	0.88	HE
3.	Builds effective teams, bringing together individuals with diverse backgrounds, skills and expertise	2.95	1.23	ME	3.06	0.74	HE
4.	Takes a proactive approach in identifying team needs and provides appropriate support.	3.04	1.09	HE	3.04	0.83	HE
5.	Promotes the one-house approach by identifying possible synergies and opportunities for collaboration with teams beyond his/her immediate area of responsibility.	3.02	0.84	HE	3.04	0.71	HE
6.	Takes action to resolve tensions and problems by identifying suitable solutions that are in compliance with the applicable organization’s regulations and rules, and by providing guidance and support to team members.	2.06	0.78	HE	3.02	0.21	
Total Mean & SD		16.85	5.74		18.51	4.26	
Grand Mean & SD		2.80	0.96		3.08	0.71	

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

Table 1. which is for research question one showed that the respondents indicated how management of teamwork competencies influence office managers’ performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State? The confirmation was made with a grand mean of 2.80 and standard deviation of 0.96 for male respondents, while that of Female respondents were 3.08 and 0.71 for mean and standard deviation. Conclusively, the result showed that to a higher extent management of teamwork competencies influence office managers’ performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State?

Research Question 2: To what extent does management of communication competencies influence office managers’ performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on management of communication competencies influence office managers’ performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State (N 122)

S/N	Item Statements	Male = 68			Female= 54		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remarks	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1.	Ability to type document	3.52	0.33	HE	2.94	1.14	HE
2.	Ability print document	2.74	0.20	ME	2.91	1.39	HE
3.	Ability to use PowerPoint	2.87	0.87	ME	3.13	0.86	HE
4.	Ability to use projector	3.01	1.05	HE	3.10	0.84	HE
5.	Ability to use graphics	2.72	1.17	ME	3.02	0.77	HE
6.	Ability to use database	3.02	1.09	HE	3.22	0.81	HE
Total Mean & SD		17.88	4.71		18.32	5.81	
Grand Mean & SD		2.98	0.78		3.05	0.96	

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

Table 2 which is for research question two showed that the respondents agreed that the management of communication competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State to a moderate and high extent respectively. The confirmation was made with a grand mean of 2.98 and 3.05 and standard deviation of 0.78 and 0.96 respectively. Conclusively, the result above revealed that the management of communication competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State to a moderate and higher extent.

Research Question 3: To what extent does management of human relations competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on management of human relations competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State (122)

S/ N	Item Statements	Male = 68			Female= 54		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remarks	\bar{x}	SD	Remarks
1.	Ability to maintain proper relations with public and fellow staff.	3.03	1.17	HE	3.02	0.77	ME
2.	Ability to have a cordial relationship with visitors.	2.52	1.12	ME	3.33	0.83	HE
3.	Ability to trains junior staff and handle difficult issues.	3.02	1.07	HE	3.05	0.91	HE
4.	Ability to delegate responsibilities to subordinates.	3.04	0.81	HE	3.22	0.88	HE
5.	Ability to accord respect to everybody in the organization	2.87	0.87	ME	3.13	0.86	HE
6.	Ability to make referral duties with tact.	3.01	1.05	HE	3.10	0.84	HE
Total Mean & SD		17.49	6.09		18.85	5.09	
Grand Mean & SD		2.91	1.01		3.14	0.84	

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

Table 3 which is for research question three showed the management of human relations competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State with a grand mean of 2.91 and standard deviation of 1.01 for male respondents and a grand mean of 3.14 and standard deviation of 0.98 for female respondents respectively. By conclusion, the above result indicates that management of human relationship competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery to a higher extent in public parastatals in Rivers State. competencies influence Office Managers and Employees Performance in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Tests of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between management of teamwork competencies and office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Table 4: r-test Analysis on management of teamwork competencies and office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	α	r-cal	r-crit	Decision
Teamwork	122	2.80	0.96	173	0.05	1.08	1.96	Accepted
Performance and Economic Recovery	122	3.08	0.71					

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

From the r-test in Table 4 above, the calculated value is 1.08 while the t critical value is 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. The r-calculated value is lesser than r-critical value, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This indicates that management of teamwork competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between management of communication competencies and office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Table 5: r-test Analysis of the There is no significant relationship between management of communication competencies and office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	α	r-cal	r-crit	Decision
Communication	122	2.98	0.78	173	0.05	0.66	1.96	Accepted
Performance and Economic Recovery	122	3.05	0.96					

Source: Field Survey, (2024).

From the r-test in table 4.8 above, the r-calculated value of 0.66 is less than r-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 levels of significance and 175 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected, meaning that management of communication competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between management of human relations competencies and office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Table 6: r-test Analysis of the relationship between management of human relations competencies and office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	α	r-cal	r-crit	Decision
Human Relations	122	2.91	1.01	175	0.05	1.39	1.96	Accepted
Level of performance	122	3.14	0.84					

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

From the r-test in table 4.6 above, the r-calculated value of 1.39 is less than r-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 levels of significance and 175 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that the

management of human relations competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

Finding from research question one which sought to ascertain the teamwork skills competencies influence Office Managers and employees' performance in public parastatals in Rivers State, with a grand mean of 2.80 and standard deviation of 0.96 for male respondents and a grand mean of 3.08 and standard deviation of 0.71 for female respondents respectively. By conclusion, the above result indicates that management of teamwork competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State. The high level of competitiveness in the labour market and ongoing innovation produce demands that require a variety of skills, high levels of specialist knowledge, rapid responses and adaptability; it is only through teamwork that these needs can be met (Kozlowski, & Ilgen, 2020). Teamwork should therefore be considered a key factor and a source of competitive advantage (Rousseau, Aubé, & Savoie, 2018; Tjosvold, 2021).

Secondly, it was revealed that the which is for research question two showed that the respondents indicated that management of communication competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State. The confirmation was made with a grand mean of 2.80 and standard deviation of 0.96 for RSU respondents, while that of IAUE respondents were 3.08 and 0.71 for mean and standard deviation. Conclusively, the result showed that the management of communication competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State. This is supported by opinion of Dambo (2011) that communication is the process by which understandable information is exchanged between two or more individuals in a system to initiate action. It involves the act of conveying thoughts of feeling to other people or receiving in return in accordance with the purpose and manner of the act (Chukwumezie, 2014). In line with the assertion above, Elendu (2018) stated that communication is the process of conveying information from one person or group of persons, department or organization to another, through post, telephone, or by any other means which includes, memorandum, reports, minutes, notices etc.

Finding from research question three which sought to ascertain the management of human relation competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State, with a grand mean of 2.91 and standard deviation of 1.01 for male respondents and a grand mean of 3.14 and standard deviation of 0.98 for female respondents respectively. By conclusion, the above result indicates that Management of teamwork competencies influence office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

This finding is also supported by the opinion of Iheriohanma (2018) stated that individual competence skills are those set of attitudes and personality traits by an individual prior to the individual's engagement into one occupation or the other. Personal skills are needed by office managers for excellent performance (Ejekam, 2021). Obedience to superior officers, self-competence and control, punctuality and regularity to work, drive and determination and general knowledge, sense of judgment and initiative, integrity, cooperation with colleagues and good human relations with the public, concentration on the job, keeping of office and business secrets, acceptance of responsibilities, capacity to work under pressure are all indispensable and required by an office manager for successful performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher therefore concludes that the managing organizational competencies for office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State. In addition, it was revealed that there is a relationship between teamwork, communication, and human relations competencies for office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the findings, the researcher recommends that:

The managing organizational competencies for office managers' performance and economic recovery in public parastatals in Rivers State, as it will enhance their work performance.

1. Office Managers in private & public parastatals should explore communication skills to enable effectively carryout their administrative duties.
2. Office Managers should update their information communication and technology skills as it has the ability to enhance work performance.
3. Office Managers should be given the opportunity be trained and retrain on other office managerial skills to enhance their performance.

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